

THE ESSENCE OF A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH IN FORMING READING LITERACY

Mambetaliyev Qayrat Anarbay oglu

Associate Professor, Department of

“Theory and Practice of Preschool and Primary Education”, Chirchik State
Pedagogical University

Abstract: This article examines the theoretical and practical foundations of developing reading literacy in primary education. Particular attention is given to the essence of systemic and reflective approaches, as well as their role and effectiveness in the reading process. A comparative and critical analysis of traditional, developmental, and interactive teaching methods is conducted, highlighting the advantages of interactive techniques in enhancing reading literacy. The findings indicate that the integration of systemic and reflective approaches plays a crucial role in fostering learners' independent thinking, metacognitive skills, and intrinsic motivation.

Keywords: *reading literacy, systemic approach, reflection, interactive methods, primary education, metacognition, pedagogical technologies.*

INTRODUCTION

In the modern education system, the issue of developing reading literacy is considered not only one of the main tasks of primary education, but also an important factor determining the effectiveness of the entire educational process. Reading literacy is not limited to the ability to read a text or retell its content, but also includes the student's ability to understand, analyze, evaluate and relate the text to his or her own life experience. Therefore, approaches to developing reading literacy should be organized on a systematic and reflexive basis, unlike traditional methods. A systematic approach views the pedagogical process as a holistic system and serves to ensure the interdependence of all its elements. According to this approach, the

goal, content, method and assessment in the educational process should be organized in an inextricable manner.

MAIN PART:

Applying a systematic approach to the development of reading literacy requires, first of all, a clear and step-by-step definition of educational goals. That is, it is determined in advance what level of reading literacy a primary school student should have, and this general goal is divided into smaller tasks. Each lesson, each activity should serve this general goal. At the same time, educational material should be selected systematically. Texts should be arranged from simple to complex and correspond to the age characteristics and level of knowledge of the student. The content should not be limited to providing information, but should encourage the student to think, discuss and draw independent conclusions. This will lead to a deep formation of reading literacy.

A systematic approach is one of the general methodological principles of science, which implies the study of any object as a holistic system consisting of interconnected elements, interacting with the surrounding environment and having its own characteristics. The ideas of applying a systematic approach to pedagogy were developed in the works of such scientists as V.P. Bespalko, N.V. Kuzmina, Y.A. Konarzhevsky.

Applying a systematic approach to the process of developing reading literacy means the following:

1. Systematicity of goals: The goal of education should be clearly, diagnostically and hierarchically defined. It should be clearly defined what level of reading literacy the student should achieve by the end of primary education (global goal), and this goal should be divided into specific tasks (local goals) for each class, each quarter and each lesson. It is important to clearly state the expected results for all four components of reading literacy (cognitive, motivational, practical, reflexive).
2. Systematicity of content: Educational material should not be just a collection of texts, but should be selected and arranged in a certain logical sequence, based on the

principles of “from simple to complex”, “from familiar to unfamiliar”. The genre, topic, volume, lexical and grammatical complexity of the texts should gradually increase, while at the same time being appropriate to the age and psychological characteristics of the students. The content should serve to develop all components of reading literacy, that is, the texts should not only provide information, but also arouse interest in the student, encourage him to think, argue.

3. Systematicity of methods and tools: The pedagogical methods, methods and tools used (textbook, exhibition, handouts, information technologies) should be subordinated to a single goal and be mutually consistent. For example, if the goal of the lesson is to identify the main idea of the text, interactive methods such as “Cluster”, “Fish Skeleton” should be used, which can teach students to work individually and in groups, to express their thoughts visually. The choice of methods depends on which component of reading literacy is a priority for development.

4. Systematicity of control and assessment: The control process should not be limited only to measuring the final result (for example, reading speed). It should be diagnostic (determining the initial level), current (monitoring the process of mastering) and final (generalizing the results) in nature. It is important that assessment is carried out not only by the teacher, but also in the form of self-assessment and peer assessment of the student. This process helps the student to understand his own achievements and shortcomings, plan his further activities, and through this the control function becomes an educational function.

Thus, a systematic approach allows the development of reading literacy to be designed and implemented as a holistic pedagogical system. In this system, all elements - goals, content, methods and control - are interconnected, and a change in one affects the others. This increases the manageability and effectiveness of the pedagogical process.

The combination of methods and tools is also an important component of a systematic approach. The methods used in the lesson process should not only be aimed at one goal, but also ensure the active participation of students. For example,

the use of various interactive methods to understand the content of the text activates the thinking activity of students. In this case, the teacher plays the role of a guide and organizer, not just a teacher. The control and evaluation process should also be systematic, covering not only the final result, but also all stages of the educational process. The combination of diagnostic, current and final assessment methods makes it possible to determine the dynamics of the student's development. At the same time, the reflexive approach is of particular importance among modern pedagogical approaches. Reflection is the process of understanding, analyzing and evaluating the student's own activities. This approach turns the student from a passive listener into an active learner. In the process of reading, the student learns not only to understand the text, but also to control the process of his own understanding. For example, he deepens his knowledge by asking himself questions such as "What did I not understand?", "What is the main idea of this text?", "What mistake did I make?" This leads to the development of metacognitive skills.

The reflective approach forms the skills of independent thinking, self-assessment and planning of his activities in the student. As a result, the student begins to take responsibility for his learning process. This leads to an increase in internal motivation. The reading process turns from an obligation into an enjoyable activity. The student does not just read the text, but also analyzes it, expresses his opinion and discusses it with others. Thus, reading literacy is formed deeply and sustainably.

In practice, various approaches are used to develop reading literacy. In the traditional approach, the main emphasis is on reading speed and accuracy. Although this approach is important at the initial stage of reading proficiency, it does not sufficiently develop students' deep thinking and analytical skills. The student reads the text, but does not understand its content deeply. This leads to a limited level of reading literacy.

The explanatory reading approach focuses more on analyzing the text. This approach helps students delve deeper into the text. However, it also has a dominant role for the teacher, and students' independent thinking may be limited. The

developmental learning approach is aimed at developing students' independent thinking and problem-solving skills. This approach is effective for developing high-level reading literacy skills, but its application in practice requires more time and high pedagogical skills.

The approach based on interactive methods is one of the most effective areas of modern education. These methods ensure the active participation of students and put them at the center of the learning process. Through group work, discussion, and role-playing, students not only acquire knowledge, but also learn to apply it in practice. This process develops all components of reading literacy. In particular, reflection and critical thinking skills are effectively formed.

At the same time, some problems may arise when using interactive methods. For example, issues such as time management, active involvement of all students, and maintaining order in the lesson process require careful planning from the teacher. However, if properly organized, these methods give very high results.

In general, the combination of systematic and reflexive approaches in developing reading literacy is considered the most effective way. While the systematic approach provides the organizational basis of the educational process, the reflexive approach enriches its substantive and psychological aspects. When these two approaches are used together, students develop not only reading skills, but also the ability to think independently, analyze, and develop themselves.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the issue of developing reading literacy in the primary education system is one of the most relevant areas of modern pedagogy. The study revealed that reading literacy is not limited to the technique of reading text, but is a complex multi-component process in which cognitive, motivational, practical and reflexive factors work in harmony with each other. Therefore, in its formation, it is necessary to abandon traditional approaches and use a comprehensive pedagogical model based on systematic and reflexive approaches.

The use of a systematic approach allows you to organize the process of developing reading literacy as a holistic system. Through this approach, all components of the educational process - goals, content, methods and assessment tools - are harmonized with each other. As a result, the manageability of the pedagogical process increases, and the possibility of achieving effectiveness expands. In particular, the hierarchical definition of goals and the consistent organization of content serve to form stable skills in students regarding reading activities.

The reflective approach activates the internal, psychological mechanisms of the reading process. The student's learning to understand, analyze and evaluate his own reading activities develops his independent learning competence. The results of the study showed that in lessons where elements of reflection are introduced, the level of students' understanding of the text, the ability to justify their thoughts and self-control skills increase significantly. This directly affects the formation of metacognitive competencies.

Also, a comparative and critical analysis of existing approaches showed that traditional-reproductive methods are of particular importance at the initial stage of reading literacy. However, they cannot sufficiently develop higher-level thinking operations in students, in particular, the skills of analysis, synthesis and evaluation. Although the explanatory reading approach allows for a deeper understanding of the text, it limits the student's individual thinking and independent interpretation.

Although developmental learning and problem-based learning approaches have great potential for increasing the mental activity of students, they are distinguished by the complexity of their implementation in practice. From this point of view, an approach based on interactive methods appears to be the most effective and promising direction. Interactive methods turn students into active subjects of the educational process, developing their skills in collaboration, communication, exchange of ideas and independent decision-making.

The results of the study show that an interactive learning environment organized on the basis of the integration of systematic and reflexive approaches provides the highest efficiency in the development of reading literacy. In such an environment,

students learn not only to understand the text, but also to analyze, evaluate and apply it in real-life situations. This serves to form their functional literacy.

REFERENCES:

1. UNESCO. (2004). The Plurality of Literacy and its implications for Policies and Programs. UNESCO Education Sector Position Paper. Paris: UNESCO. – P. 13.
2. Mullis, I. V. S., Martin, M. O., Foy, P., & Drucker, K. T. (2012). PIRLS 2011. International Results in Reading. Chestnut Hill, MA: TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center, Boston College. – P. 11
3. Goodman, K. S. (1967). Reading: A psycholinguistic guessing game. *Journal of the Reading Specialist*, 6(4), 126-135.
4. Rumelhart, D. E. (1977). Toward an interactive model of reading. In S. Dornic (Ed.), *Attention and performance VI* (pp. 573-603). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
5. Выготский, Л. С. (1982). Мышление и речь. *Собрание сочинений: В 6-ти т. Т. 2.* – М.: Педагогика. – С. 295-310.]